

IMPACT OF CUTTING PARAMETERS ON SURFACE QUALITY DURING MILLING OF AISI 1055 AND AISI 4140 STEELS

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ABSTRACT: This study explores and contrasts the surface roughness caused by milling AISI 1055 steel and AISI 4140 steel. The materials underwent heat treatment, especially quenching and tempering at different temperatures. The evaluation was performed utilizing both multifactorial and unifactorial methodologies. The testing used a complete factorial design with eight variants, and the sample size was 2^3 ($N = 8$). The findings indicate that an increase in rotation frequency N correlates with a reduction in surface roughness R_a for both materials across different tempering temperatures. At a tempering temperature of 550 °C, the surface roughness R_a values are much higher for both materials than at lower temperatures (200 and 300 °C). Additionally, test No. 5 indicates that the ideal surface quality for the AISI 1055 material was achieved when tempered at 550 °C. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized to assess the effect of cutting parameters on surface quality. The feed rate (f) was determined to be the principal factor for the two materials examined, while the rotation frequency (N) served as the secondary effect. Two mathematical methods are presented to quantify R_a , the surface roughness of the two materials. Finding the appropriate cutting settings using MATLAB software resulted in a 35% increase in the surface quality of AISI 1055 steel compared to AISI 4140 steel. To achieve improved surface quality when milling materials treated at elevated tempering temperatures, it is recommended to use AISI 1055 steel instead of AISI 4140 steel.

KEYWORDS: (Design experiment, Roughness, ANOVA, Optimization, Steels)

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their high productivity and precision, the machine parts are widely used in the milling process. Generally, we estimate the machinability of this process based on factors like machining quality, cutting force, material removal rate, and tool wear. To quantify machining quality, the standard for the mean surface roughness criterion is often used to characterize the damage caused by the machining process. It is commonly recognized that a material's mechanical characteristics and machinability are significantly affected by its surface roughness. As a result, a lot of basic research has been carried out to simulate the surface texture in this area and estimate the surface roughness in milling processes (Montgomery, 1991; Ehmann, 1994; and Layegh, 2017). The results of Son (Son, 2020) show that in the literature on surface roughness, almost 94% of the research papers choose cutting parameters as the input parameters for experimental research. To

characterize this surface condition, we use roughness as a geometric parameter, and we consider it one of the most important aspects of machining. Kim et al. (Kim, 2021) investigated the roughness of C45 steel using P6M5 tools during milling. According to the study, the feed rate has the greatest effect on the surface roughness, whereas the cutting depth and speed have less influence. Bembenek et al. (Bembenek, 2023) discovered that while milling AISI 304 material, the feed per tooth parameter had the greatest impact on the final surface roughness. These results were confirmed by visual and numerical analyses. Kadirgama et al. (Kadirgama, 2009) have shown that the RSM method for roughness is successful for different combinations of cutting parameters. In their study, Nexhat et al. (Nexhat, 2018) used variance analysis to find the most important factors that affect surface roughness when 42CrMo4 steels are milled on a CNC machine. They concluded that material hardness, feed rate, and cutting speed are the three most crucial parameters.

Yusufl et al. (Yusufl, 2010) showed that the most essential components affecting surface quality in the Taguchi process are spindle speed and tool type, followed by machining depth and feed rate. According to an analysis of the variance in machined stainless steel's surface roughness (Zerti, 2019), the feed rate has an 80.71% influence on the surface roughness, and the cutting depth is only 2.99%. When optimizing the supplied parameters, such as radial cutting depth, feed rate, and cutting speed, it was discovered that the spindle and tool speed have a significant influence on surface roughness. (Thanasuptawee, 2018; Rahman, 2021; and Ropyak, 2021). Sathyamoorthy and İşleyen (Sathyamoorthy, 2017; and İşleyen, 2019) said that surface roughness affects the cutting depth and spindle speed when milling magnesium alloy AM60 and fiberboard MDF.

Stipkovic et al. (Stipkovic, 2018) found that feed rate was mainly responsible for controlling surface roughness when facing AISI 4140 steel. Arruda et al. (Arruda, 2019) used a response surface approach and a robust parametric design to create an optimization model to find the surface roughness of AISI H13 steel during the finishing process. Experiments were carried out on a CNC milling machine with HSS cutting tools on 7075 T6 aluminum alloy (Sakhivelu, 2017). The feed rate mainly determines the surface roughness, while the depth of cut mainly determines the material removal rate. In the CNC milling process, Saxena et al. (Saxena, 2017) used the Taguchi technique to discover the ideal cutting parameters for the surface roughness of 6061 aluminum. The spindle speed has the greatest influence on the surface condition after feed, tool type, and cutting depth. Confirmatory test results showed that the Taguchi technique was effective in optimizing machining parameters to minimize surface roughness.

Mechanical workshops in the Maghreb region attempt to attain improved surface quality when milling AISI 1055 and AISI 4140 materials with P35 carbide inserts. In this comparative analysis, we assess the impact of the machining parameters on the surface roughness of the two steels as well as the effectiveness of the prediction models using ANOVA. Additionally, using the fmincon function from the MATLAB toolbox to optimize the surface roughness (Ra), we were able to identify the best cutting parameters for each material. Finally, a recommendation was made to pick and use one of these materials at the company level.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1 Design of experiments

The The experiments were performed using a full-factorial design with eight combinations (Bradley, 2020). The purpose of this study is to look at the influence of various cutting settings on surface quality. It considers three parameters: the depth of cut (ap), the feed (f), and the cutting speed (Vc). For both materials investigated, the surface roughness Ra was used as the response or output function.

2.2 Materials and methods

The steels AISI 4140 and AISI 1055 were used to create the parallelepiped specimens, which had cross sections of 30 × 40 mm. Shafts, cylinder blocks, crankshafts, and other transmission components are commonly made from AISI 4140, low-alloy steel. Due to its chromium, molybdenum, and vanadium composition, it is categorized as a thermal shock-resistant steel. The second material, AISI 1055, is carbon steel with heat treatments and no indicated weldability. This material is utilized for parts subjected to impact stress and has extremely good resistance. (Applications: guide pins, gears, worms, bearings, sprockets, bolts, etc.). The chemical compositions of the two materials are reported as follows (in percent by weight).

AISI 4140: C 0.43; Cr 0.90; Mo 0.209; V 0.001; Si 0.25; Mn 0.71; S 0.004; P 0.14; Fe 0.9; Cu 0.13; Al 0.12; W 0.01; Ni 0.01.

AISI 1055: C 0.56; Cr 0.014; Mo 0.001; V 0.003; Si 0.30; Mn 0.74; S 0.002; P 0.002; Sn 0.001; Cu 0.012; Al 0.003; Ni 0.047.

2.3 Heat treatment of materials

Both materials' hardness was measured at various tempering temperatures. (Table 1).

Table 1. Hardness at different temperatures

Nuance	Average hardness (HRC) after tempering at T°		
	200 °C	300 °C	550 °C
AISI1055	60.1	58.16	50.26
AISI4140	58.66	57.56	48.76

The materials were quenched and tempered at different temperatures (Table 2). The heat treatments were conducted within an industrial furnace (250 °C/h, T° max. 1200 °C, weight max. 50 kg).

Table 2. Heat treatments of both materials

Treatment procedure	Quenching		Tempering	
	AISI 1055	AISI 4140	AISI 1055	AISI 4140
Heating duration (min)	45	60	60	60
Heating Temperature(T°C)	850	850	200 300 550	200 300 550
Holding time (min)	20	30	90	180
Cooling (T°C)	20° with water	20° with water	To air	To air

2.4 Machining conditions

The experiments were conducted using the SXB 623 CNC milling machine. These machines can reach up to 2100 rpm and have a spindle power of 14.9 kW. A milling cutter with a 32 mm diameter was used for the processing. The P35 (GC2030-SANDVIK) triangular metal-carbide inserts are attached, and their tip radius is $R\epsilon = 0.5$ mm. Using the PVD-coated grade [TiN+TiAlN], low-carbon steels with built-up cutting edges are milled. It is perfect for milling a variety of single- and multi-layer materials at 90 degrees. In the machining of cemented carbides, coatings on cemented carbide inserts are frequently utilized (Selinder, 1998). The cutting parameters were established using Table 3.

Table 3. Ranges of cutting parameters

Parameters	Methods	
	Unifactorial	Multifactorial
Rotation frequency N (rpm)	700 - 750 800 - 850 900 - 950 1000 - 1050	1000 - 2000
Feed rate f (mm/min)	60	60 - 160
Depth of cut ap (mm)	0.6	0.6 - 1.5

2.5 Roughness measurements

One measurable property of a surface that quantifies high-frequency departures from an ideal surface is surface roughness. To express this parameter, the average arithmetic roughness Ra (μm) is typically utilized. The most often-used metric is average roughness, since it offers a fundamental

approximation for crucial decisions (Altan, 2001). Using a Mitutoyo roughness meter, the machined surfaces' quality was evaluated in both tests against a single standard (Ra). A sample that was subjected to a tempering temperature of 550 °C had its surface roughness Ra measured.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Material hardness

Table 1 shows that the hardness decreases for the two types of materials, and the curves are essentially similar (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Hardness development

As the temperature increases, the hardness of AISI 1055 and AISI 4140 materials decreases, reaching 48.76 and 50.26 HRC, respectively. At 550 °C, AISI 1055 has a slightly higher hardness than AISI 4140. Therefore, the similar hardness of the two materials at the tempering temperature of 550 °C would have the same effect on surface roughness. Therefore, the influence of this hardness on the roughness of the surface was excluded.

3.2 Roughness assessment

To conduct the experiments, a full-factorial design with eight combinations was used. The surface roughness Ra values obtained using the single-factorial and multifactorial methods are listed in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. Results of the surface roughness Ra (unifactorial method)

No Test	N rpm	f mm/mn	ap mm	Ra (μm) at					
				200 °C		300 °C		550 °C	
				AISI		AISI		AISI	
				1055	4140	1055	4140	1055	4140
1	700	60	0.6	0.42	0.43	0.60	0.57	2.75	3.80
2	750	60	0.6	0.40	0.41	0.51	0.49	2.10	3.24
3	800	60	0.6	0.34	0.35	0.45	0.43	1.80	3.01
4	850	60	0.6	0.30	0.32	0.43	0.41	1.05	2.24

5	900	60	0.6	0.28	0.30	0.33	0.31	0.38	1.43
6	950	60	0.6	0.25	0.24	0.28	0.26	0.31	0.37
7	1000	60	0.6	0.21	0.23	0.26	0.24	0.98	1.02
8	1050	60	0.6	0.18	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.21	0.26

Table 5. Results of the surface roughness Ra (multifactorial method)

No Test	N rpm	f mm/mm	apmm	Ra (µm) at 550 °C	
				AISI	
				1055	4140
1	1000	60	0.6	0.98	1.02
2	2000	60	0.6	0.47	0.79
3	1000	160	0.6	0.30	0.47
4	2000	160	0.6	0.18	0.26
5	1000	60	1.5	0.61	1.11
6	2000	60	1.5	0.31	1.09
7	1000	160	1.5	0.61	0.57
8	2000	160	1.5	1.10	0.54

The results shown in Table 4 and depicted in Figure 2 demonstrate that as the rotation frequency N increases, the surface roughness Ra of the two materials diminishes at varying tempering temperatures, indicating improved surface quality.

Fig. 2 The Influence of the rotation frequency N on the roughness Ra at different tempering temperatures

At 300°C, AISI 4140 has a lower surface roughness than AISI 1055 (Fig. 2). It is also important to note that the best surface finishes (Ra = 0.18 µm and Ra = 0.20 µm) were obtained in Test No. 8 (N = 1050 rpm) when milling AISI 1055 and AISI 4140, respectively. The two materials exhibited stark differences in surface roughness at a tempering temperature of T = 550°C, with one showing a significant increase from 4% to 276%. Test No. 5 (N = 900 rpm) demonstrated the greatest difference in roughness between the two materials, with AISI

1055 emerging as the clear winner (Ra AISI 4140 was more than 276% higher than Ra AISI 1055).

3.3 Statistical analysis

Statistical examination of the findings from Table 5 enabled us to ascertain the influence of cutting parameters on the quality of the final surface. Tables 6 and 7 display the findings of the ANOVA and detail the primary variables and interactions influencing surface roughness. The evaluation was conducted using a significance level of 5% and a confidence level of 95%. The ANOVA displayed in Tables 6 and 7 elucidates the most important components and interactions.

Table 6. Roughness Ra variance analysis of AISI 4140

Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-ratio	P value
A: N rpm	0,21994	1	0,21994	274,94	0,0383
B: f mm/mm	0,26357	1	0,26357	329,47	0,0350
C: ap mm	0,00200	1	0,00200	2,51	0,3586
AB	0,17405	1	0,17405	217,56	0,0431
AC	0,00405	1	0,00405	5,06	0,2662
BC	0,0242	1	0,0242	30,25	0,1145
Total error	0,0008	1	0,0008		
Total (corr.)	0,7548	7			

Table 7. Roughness Ra variance analysis of AISI 1055

Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-ratio	P value
A:N rpm	0,02239	1	0,02239	199,10	0,0450
B: f mm/mm	0,03834	1	0,03834	340,85	0,0344
C: ap mm	0,00120	1	0,00120	10,70	0,1889
AB	0,00001	1	0,00001	0,11	0,7952
AC	0,01901	1	0,01901	169,00	0,0489
BC	0,00001	1	0,00001	0,11	0,7952
Total error	0,00011	1	0,00011		
Total (corr.)	0,71188	7			

AISI 4140: P value (f) = 0.0350 < 5%; P value (N) = 0.0383 < 5%

AISI 1055: P value (f) = 0.0344 < 5%; P value (N) = 0.0450 < 5%

The Pareto charts shown in Figures 3 and 4 also provide information on the most significant factors and interactions. The results show that feed rate (f)

and rotation frequency (N) have the most significant effects on surface roughness (Ra) for both materials studied. Other materials yielded similar results [Yusufi, Zerti, Stipkovic, Arruda and Saxena]. These are followed by the products of the variables N*f and N*ap for AISI 4140 and AISI 1055 materials, respectively. The other elements have no impact on the surface roughness.

Fig. 3 Pareto chart (AISI 1055)

Fig. 4 Pareto chart (AISI 4140)

Furthermore, the analysis of these results allowed us to identify the mathematical models of roughness Ra given by Eqs. (1 and 2).

- Mathematical models:

$$Ra_{AISI\ 1050} = 2,5393 - 0,0011 * N - 0,01426 * f - 0,1355 * ap + 0,0000059 * N * f + 0,0001 * N * ap + 0,00244 * f * ap \quad (1)$$

$$Ra_{AISI\ 4140} = 1,6302 - 0,00035 * N - 0,00544 * f - 0,105 * ap + 5.E - 8 * N * f + 0,00021 * N * ap - 0,000055 * f * ap \quad (2)$$

The tested materials' surface roughness Ra models were evaluated using the correlation coefficients R² and modified R² (Table 8). The results show that the suggested regression equations provide an excellent description of the responses.

Table 8. Modeling correlation coefficients

Nuance	Correlation coefficient R ² %	Adjusted correlation coefficient R ² adj% %
AISI 1055	99.89	99.25
AISI 4140	99.98	99.88

3.4 Optimization

According to Eq. (3) (Berthiau, 2001), an optimization problem (P) of the type minimization or maximization of n dimensions can be expressed as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & \text{Max } f_{obj}(x) \\ & x \in R^n \quad i = 1, \dots, p \\ & g_i(x) \leq 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, q \\ & h_j(x) = 0 \\ & x_{min} \leq x \leq x_{max} \end{aligned} \right\} (3)$$

It is a minimization or maximization criterion, also known as an objective function.

x, xmax, and xmin are the unknown vectors or limits of the achievable range.

h_j(x) and g_i(x) are the current equality and inequality constraints. A set of settings offers a resolution to the problem. A collection of parameters (x) gives the solution to the problem, while the objective function denotes the minimum of the equations, inequalities, and domain restrictions. We used MATLAB's fmincon function to minimize the surface roughness objective function, then outlined the problem using the following equation No. 4.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & Ra > 0 \\ & \text{Subject to } 1000 \leq N \leq 2000 \\ & 6 \leq f \leq 160 \\ & 0.6 \leq ap \leq 1.5 \end{aligned} \right\} (4)$$

To solve the above system, the following program was created using MATLAB's Optimtool to call the preprogrammed slice function.

function, [x, lambda, grad, Hessian, output, fval, exit flag, and x] = untitled1(x0, lb, ub).

The default settings were used.

Options = optim options ('fmincon');

Adjust the option configuration.

Options optimization options (options, Display', 'off');

Options = optim options (options, 'Plot-Fcn, { @optimplotconstrviolation, @optimplotfirstorderopt, @optimplotfval})).

[x, fval, lambda, grad, Hessian, output, exit flag, and options] = ...

“fmincon(@mynonlcon, options, lb, ub, @obj fun, x0, [], [], [], [], [])”.

The search for the optimal values for the two materials studied resulted in an improvement of 35% in the surface quality of AISI 1055 steel compared to that of AISI 4140 (see Table 9).

Table 9. Optimal surface roughness (Ra)

Nuance	Cutting parameters			Ra(μm) optimum
	μ N (rpm)	f(mm/min)	ap (mm)	
AISI 1055	1999.996	160	0.6	0.189
AISI 4140	1999.998	160	0.6	0.257

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Using a P35 milling tool, an experimental comparative study on milling-treated AISI 1055 and AISI 4140 steels produced the following findings:

- The hardness of both materials diminishes roughly uniformly when the tempering temperature is elevated to $T = 550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- At varying tempering temperatures, the surface roughness (Ra) of the two machined steels enhances with an increase in rotation frequency (N).
- When tempering at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, AISI 1055 outperforms AISI 4140 in terms of surface quality.
- In test No. 5 at a tempering temperature of $550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the AISI 1055 material outperformed the AISI 4140 material in terms of surface quality.
- The analysis of variance revealed that feed rate (f) had the greatest impact on surface roughness (Ra) for both materials, followed by rotation frequency (N).
- The R2 correlation coefficient results validate the suggested surface roughness model.
- Optimizing the surface quality of AISI 1055 steel led to a 35% improvement over AISI 4140.
- To guarantee better surface quality in the workshop, it is recommended to carry out milling operations using treated AISI 1055 steel.

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